

Original Article

Comparative Study of Us and Indian Feration

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India and the US are the popular democratic governments in the world. Both are having a federal form of governments, but the nature and functions differ from one another. Though, both have the basic features of a federal system, we find lots of differences in their framework. Dual Governments, Written Constitution, Bicameral legislature, Sharing of Revenue, Amendment Procedure, Federal Judiciary seems common features between the two countries, but there are many differences their style of functioning and operations. The basic differences found between the two systems are mainly the rigidity of the constitution, distribution of powers, judicial system, dissolution of State governments, veto power and few others. This papers is mainly concerned with system of the functioning of the federation.

Key Words: Federal, Union, Government, Constitution, Judiciary, Amendment, Veto Power, President

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Introduction:

Comparative study of different system is useful for the student of political science to have better and definite idea of the system prevailing in a country. At the same time it enables him to analyse the merits and demerits of different systems, enabling him to find out which system fits to which country. In this context the Study of US and Indian federation is taken up in this paper to understand the systems properly. In this article a sincere effort is made to understand and analyse the operative political system of these two democratic systems. The best known and earliest such comparative study of constitutions was by Aristotle, the father of Political Science, who studied 158 constitutions, to establish a best form of government. After the Second World War the study of Comparative Government and Politics gained momentum. According to Freeman, "Comparative politics is comparative analysis of various forms of Government and diverse political institutions." Here the author feels that in a federation analyzing the government and the existing institutions is important. M. G. Smith, defines, 'Comparative politics is the study of the forms of political organizations, their properties, correlations, variations and modes of change.' The changes that are taking place, the relations among the organs and their properties are studied. India and the US are not just the biggest democracies, they are strongest and to many extent older also. America became a Republic in 1789 and India in 1950. Both have adopted a federal form government, but under different conditions. The form government existing in both the States are completely different as US has a Presidential system whereas India is having Parliamentary Government. Both Governments derive their powers as per their constitution and carry on their administration accordingly.

Similar Characters:

The student of Political Science/Constitution can find few similitude and distinctions between the two federations. Both the nations became Republics by adopting the constitution. The framers of the Indian Constitution brought certain features, from the American system, which were suitable to our political culture. So, we can find these common features among the two States.

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Written Constitution:

Both the Republics have a written Constitution, based on that, the Federal Government in America and Union Government in India are established. Both the Constitutions are drafted by the expert committee. These Governments derive their legislative, administrative, executive, judicial and other powers from the Constitution. The US Constitution was enforced in 1789 and that of India in 1950. During these years lot of changes have taken place in various fields and new subjects have emerged. So to meet these changes, both the Constitutions have given scope for amendments as per the requirement of the time.

Rights:

Both the Constitutions have granted certain Rights to its citizens, in US they are the Bill of Rights, which were added to the constitution through first ten amendments. The Constitution of India on the other side had given seven Fundamental Rights to its citizens in the Third chapter, from Article 12 to 35, but Right to Property is no more a Fundamental Rights, as it was removed from the list by 44th Constitutional Amendment Act. In both the countries these Rights are justiciable.

Strong Central Government:

Federal Constitution of both the States have made the Central Government strong. The Federal or Union Government has supreme powers in many matters. The US federation has 50 States, whereas in India 28 States and 9 Union territories . Important National powers are with the Federal government, but some minor subjects of local importance are with the States. In case of conflict on the subjects in the Concurrent list, the Federal government law prevails over the State law.

Bicameral Legislature:

Both the federations have bicameral legislature , the Lower House giving representation to the people of the Nation, (which is also known as popular House) and the Upper House gives representation to the States. The Upper House in the US is known as Senate and that of India is Council of States (Rajya Sabha) and the Lower House is the House of Representatives in the US and House of the People(Lok Sabha) in India. Both the Houses are established as per the respective Constitutions and derive their power from the Constitution.

Seperation of Powers:

The Constitution of both the Federations have three organs of the Government, which derive their powers accordingly. These three organs perform different functions. The legislature (Congress in US and Parliament in India) is a law making organ, the Executive (The President in US and Cabinet under the leadership of PM) looks after the administration by enforcing the laws and the Judiciary interprets the laws and assure reparations.

System of Checks-N-Balances:

The three organs of the Government have supreme power in their sphere. They are free to exercise them according to constitutional provisions as per the requirement. But, there is a saying, 'Absolute power corrupts absolutely.' So, both the countries have given powers to its organs, but to control the misuse of it, certain limitations are imposed on them. In the US the President has supreme executive powers under Article II . It empowers him to appoint ministers, conclude into treaties with other countries, and make major appointments like Ambassadors, Consuls, Judges and other officers, being Commander-in-Chief of Armed forces appoint heads of armed force and enforce laws. All these are to be ratified by the Senate, then only they are enforced. He is subject to impeachment by the Legislature. By delaying appointments and using veto power , he controls the Congress. The judiciary has the power of verifying the constitutionality of a law. In India, the Cabinet enjoys executive powers. But the Parliament may dismiss the Government by passing a vote of no confidence. It can reject the bills introduced by the Government. In turn, the executive, that is the Cabinet may dissolve the Lower House of the Parliament and make the members back to common citizen. The laws passed by the Parliament are subject to verification by the Judiciary . The President has limited veto power. Thus both the federations have some measures to check the other organ from becoming arbitrary.

Republics:

Both the federations have a Republican form of Government. The head of the State in both countries are indirectly elected by the people. They are elected by the Electoral College. The term of office of the US President is four years, whereas that of the Indian counterpart is five years. In both the countries no hereditary institution exists.

Two Governments:

In America as well as India we find dual Government system. For the entire Nation you have one Government, which is called the Federal Government in US, where as in India it is known as Union or Central Government. For every the federating units we have a Government which is State Government in both the Countries. These Governments are established according to the respective Constitutions and function accordingly.

Distinctive Characters: Apart from the above similarities, we find certain distinctions between the two systems. The polity, process amendment, form of government, some unitary features are seen between the two systems.

Rigidity:

The American Constitution known for its nature. When the whole world was involved in the Second World War, Americans were conducting Presidential elections. But when it comes to Indian scenario it is neither rigid nor flexible. The Constitution of America is amended 27 times, the Indian Constitution is amended 106 times.

Form of Government:

America is following the Presidential form of government and India has Parliamentary form of government. The President in US is free from the control of legislature, but in India the executive is created, controlled and dismissed by the legislature

Party System:

America has two party system and India has multy party system. On account of this the federal government in US is stable, and that of India is unstable. For. Ex. Vajapayee government survived for just 13 days.

Inequal Representation:

The Constitution of America gives equal representation in the Upper House (Senate) to all the States. Every State has two representatives. That is not the case with Indian Constitution wherein the Upper House has in equal representation to the States depending on the population.

Ex.Karnataka sends 12representatives and Skkim 1, & Telangana 7.

Judicial System:

In America you have separate Courts for the Federation and the States, which is not found in India. We have single judicial setup.

Citezenship:

In US every citizen enjoys dual citizenship, one of the Nation, the other one is the State in which he resides, whereas in India, there is only one citizenship that is of Indian.

Constitution:

Americans have a separate Constitution for every State, which is not seen in India. Before abrogation of Article 370 Jammu & Kashmir had a separate Constitution.

Conclusion:

Though there are some common features between the two systems, some differences are also seen. Apart from the above listed distinctions Article 3, 169, 246(4), 352, 356 and 360, appointment of Governor, Grants-in-aid, all India services are not found under US federation. But both the systems are working successfully since their incorporation.

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